

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) – full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant	Dr. Joseph B. Burant
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Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Antica Čulina
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Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	SPI-Birds Data Entry Software (SPI-BirDES): closing the FAIR data life cycle on the ecology of breeding birds
Project duration	24 months

English public summary
<p>In ecology, many research groups collect similar types of data, but there are no community-defined tools for data entry. SPI-BirDES will develop an open, modular data entry platform for researchers studying wild breeding birds across the globe. This platform will make it easier for scientists to collect, organise, and standardise their field data, supporting open science and FAIR data management practices. SPI-BirDES will be designed in close collaboration with the research community and will be freely available to all users. By improving data quality and access, the platform will enable researchers to manage, integrate, and reuse valuable long-term ecological datasets.</p> <p>Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 100</p>

Dutch public summary
<p>Binnen het ecologisch onderzoek zijn er veel onderzoeksgroepen die vergelijkbare gegevens verzamelen, maar door de onderzoeksgemeenschap gedefinieerde tools voor data-invoer ontbreken. SPI-BirDES gaat een open, modulaire invoeromgeving ontwikkelen voor onderzoekers, wereldwijd, die wilde broedvogels bestuderen. Het platform faciliteert hiermee het verzamelen, organiseren en standaardiseren van veldgegevens volgens FAIR-principes, en bevordert daarmee transparantie en herbruikbaarheid. SPI-BirDES wordt in nauwe samenwerking met de onderzoeksgemeenschap ontworpen en zal vrij beschikbaar zijn voor alle gebruikers. Door de datakwaliteit en toegankelijkheid te verbeteren, ondersteunt het platform verantwoord databeheer en maakt het langlopende ecologische datasets beter bruikbaar voor integratie, analyse en hergebruik voor toekomstig onderzoek.</p> <p>Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 99</p>

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

The [SPI-Birds Network & Database](#) is a community-led initiative to facilitate scientific collaboration through the standardisation of data from studies of individually marked breeding birds [1]. Primarily, SPI-Birds develops customised pipelines to harmonise data well *after* data collection and entry (Figure 1). In the **SPI-BirDES** project, we seek to move upstream by **developing an open, modular data entry software (DES) to support the digitisation, management, and standardisation of field data**. The DES will allow researchers to manage core SPI-Birds data types and create custom modules for other data needs. Developed in close collaboration with our active community, **SPI-BirDES** addresses demand for common, flexible data entry solutions that promote strong data management practices and ensure long-tail ecological data are FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable [2]) from the start. **SPI-BirDES** embraces open science principles by building sustainable, community-driven infrastructure to increase data quality, integration, sharing, and reuse [e.g., [3]].

Word count SEC31 (max. 150): 147

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

Community | **SPI-BirDES** primarily addresses the needs of the SPI-Birds Network, a global and growing community of researchers managing long-term (often decades) datasets on breeding birds (165 studies as of 04/2025). The DES will support individual researchers and enhance collaboration across the Network. Its modular, open design will also benefit other ecological monitoring networks seeking flexible, FAIR-compliant data management infrastructure.

Challenges | Data collectors face persistent barriers to FAIR and open data practices [4]. Data are often entered using spreadsheets, outdated front-end software, or custom-built systems that lack interoperability. Such fragmented approaches pose risks to data quality, integration, and long-term access as legacy systems become obsolete or unsupported. These challenges hinder efficient data processing, complicate reuse, and reduce the security and value of long-term datasets.

Needs | This proposal was initiated through informal conversations with SPI-Birds members about their data entry approaches and needs. Responses to our recent community survey show demand is widespread: of 48 respondents, **98% supported the basic idea, 90% would consider adopting the platform, and 77% expressed a willingness to co-design it**. Respondents cited desire to improve data management, lack of tools, and dissatisfaction with current solutions—confirming a clear need for a community-driven DES.

Word count SEC32 (max. 200): 199

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

SPI-BirDES is firmly grounded in Open Science principles. The platform will be fully open source, with all code version-controlled on GitHub (<https://github.com/SPI-Birds>) and archived with DOIs via Zenodo for traceability and citation. The DES will be released under a permissive licence (e.g., [Apache 2.0](#)), supporting transparency and reuse.

The platform will implement open, community-defined metadata and data standards from SPI-Birds, enabling FAIR data practices from the point of entry. FAIR data principles are a cornerstone of Open Science [5] and the work of SPI-Birds [6], ensuring that research outputs are not only accessible, but also findable and reusable by others. Researchers will retain control over their data while benefitting from tools that support data standardisation, documentation, and reproducibility. Data entered through the platform can be linked to the SPI-Birds repository and, when permitted, made openly accessible under clearly defined access and governance frameworks.

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SPI-BirDES will be co-designed through consultation with users, with development priorities guided by input from the SPI-Birds Advisory Board. This ensures the platform will be shaped by the needs of its community and supports long-term engagement. By embedding transparent governance and iterative community feedback into its development, **SPI-BirDES** will put open, inclusive research infrastructure development into practice.

Word count SEC33 (max. 200): 200

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

Overview & Aims

SPI-BirDES will develop a modular, open-source DES to support the digitisation, management, and standardisation of ecological field data. The DES will integrate with existing SPI-Birds infrastructure (customised pipelines, metadata form) and in-development components (online repository, standard data warehouse, request interface) (Figure 1). The platform will support entry and management of core SPI-Birds data types ([Standard Protocol version 2.0](#)) and extended functionality through user-built modules (Figure 2). The goal is to ensure data are structured and documented according to FAIR data principles, while remaining flexible to meet the needs of our diverse userbase.

Figure 1 | Our proposed DES in the context of the FAIR data life cycle and existing SPI-Birds infrastructure and projects

System Design & Architecture

The DES will consist of a modular interface for data entry built on a relational backend aligned to the SPI-Birds format (Figure 2). The system will need to support both web-based and desktop deployment, enabling flexible use in the field or offline. Users will enter core SPI-Birds data types through structured data entry forms, which can be customised with species- and site-specific reference values and autofill procedures.

Figure 2 | Mock-up of the proposed modular and extendable DES, including the minimum modules for entry of SPI-Birds standard data and export to contributor-specific formats

Users will be able to define their own data entry view by selecting from reusable “building blocks” or modules. These views will be configurable to match study-specific workflows while maintaining compatibility with the SPI-Birds standard format (e.g., enforcing relational database design). A lightweight planning tool will support fieldwork by generating simple, reproducible reports (e.g., daily visit and targeted catching schedules).

Bulk data can be imported from templated spreadsheets, with built-in validation procedures to ensure consistency and relational integrity. **SPI-BirDES** will support permission management for access control and be designed with future API integration in mind.

Timeline for Implementation

1. **Community Consultation (M0-2)** | We will consult with the SPI-Birds Network and wider research community to gather input on system requirements. Building on recent discussions and survey results, we will host online roundtables and distribute design mock-ups to gather feedback.
2. **Recruitment & Onboarding (M1-3)** | We will recruit two research software engineers (RSE; [7]) with expertise in user-focussed application development. They will work closely with the SPI-Birds core team, departmental database manager, and ICT personnel at NIOO-KNAW. The recruitment committee will include RSE partners from our ongoing *FAIRBirds* project to advise on technical demands for the positions.
3. **Technical Scoping (M3-5)** | We will define the technical architecture for the DES, including technology stack selection, codebase structure, system requirements, and import/export protocols. We will also review integration options with existing SPI-Birds infrastructure, develop user stories to guide project development, and draft initial module specifications.
4. **Iterative Development (M5-18)** | Development will follow agile working methods, enabling rapid iteration and user feedback. We will prioritise the core modules, data entry, import/export, and validation, and gradually extend to field planning and user-specific configurations.
5. **Testing & Refinement (M16-22)** | Feedback from structured user testing with volunteers will be used to refine usability and functionality. We will deploy a beta version for public testing in Month 18, with finalised versions of the web and desktop applications by Month 22.
6. **Promotion & Sustainability (M20-24, Parallel)** | We will develop user documentation and tutorials, conduct outreach via SPI-Birds channels (newsletter, mailing list, BlueSky), and promote the DES to adjacent communities. Sustainability planning will be embedded in all activities. Hosting and maintenance responsibilities will be absorbed into NIOO-KNAW’s long-term infrastructure plan for SPI-Birds.

Figure 3 | *Timeline of key project activities. Milestones occur at the end of each month*

Development Methods

All development will be public and version-controlled via GitHub, with regular documentation and issue tracking. Code will be licensed to ensure reusability and transparency. Peer review, modular design and automated testing will reinforce code quality. Documentation and training materials will be developed alongside the software, ensuring usability. Functional prototypes will be shared with users at key milestones (Figure 3). A staged rollout (alpha, beta, full release) will ensure stability and a smooth user experience.

Practical Considerations

The DES will support cross-platform compatibility and require minimal installation. The web version will be hosted on dedicated NIOO-KNAW servers with ICT support. A standalone, desktop version will also be available for offline use. Data will be locally stored by default, giving researchers full control. Export features will allow conversion to the SPI-Birds standard format and secure archiving on the SPI-Birds repository. While the platform will not replicate all legacy tools, its architecture will enable adaptation to diverse user needs.

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4.2 Team composition

The project team comprises the core team of the SPI-Birds Network & Database, hosted at the Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO-KNAW). This team brings deep expertise in long-term ecological data, FAIR data management practices, metadata standardisation, and large-scale research support infrastructure. While their backgrounds are in ecology, the team members have led multiple open science initiatives and have extensive experience working at the interface of data management and infrastructure development. To implement the **SPI-BirDES** project, the core team will work together with technical staff at NIOO-KNAW and two software engineers. This interdisciplinary team will ensure the project combines strong domain-specific knowledge with the technical expertise necessary to develop a robust platform.

Name	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
Dr. J. B. (Joseph) Burant	NIOO-KNAW	Research data management, data rescue, FAIR data, population ecology	Project lead project management; coordinate consultation; liaison with funder and project partners; community engagement; sustainability planning
Dr. S. J. G. (Stefan) Vriend	NIOO-KNAW	FAIR data, metadata standards, reproducible workflows, population ecology	Co-applicant and technical co-lead SPI-Birds developer and data manager; platform architecture; integration with existing SPI-Birds infrastructure; liaises with developers
Dr. A (Antica) Culina	NIOO-KNAW	Open Science, international FAIR and Open science landscape, bird ecology	Co-applicant SPI-Birds co-founder; strategic advisor; alignment with Open Science principles and policies; community engagement
Prof. dr. M. E. (Marcel) Visser	NIOO-KNAW	Long-term ecological research, evolutionary ecology	Co-applicant SPI-Birds co-founder; senior project advisor; stakeholder engagement; support integration with (inter-)national infrastructure
Dr. J. (Judith) Risse	NIOO-KNAW	Database design, data validation workflows, bioinformatics	AnE database manager technical alignment between project and internal data management needs; testing; local deployment

NIOO-KNAW ICT personnel	NIOO-KNAW	Server maintenance, hosting infrastructure, network security	Institutional support; host web application; supports secure, stable deployment
<i>To be hired</i>	NIOO-KNAW	Modular application architecture, data modelling, backend development, bulk data handling, open-source tooling	Research Software Engineer lead backend development, including database interfacing, modular form builder, user management, and validation pipelines
<i>To be hired</i>	NIOO-KNAW	Web application development, UI/UX design, data pipelines, API development	Research Software Engineer responsible for front-end development, including interface design, field planning tools, and user workflows; lead usability testing; documentation support; develop long-term extensibility features

Word count SECTION 4.2 (max. 350): 350

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and Impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Delay in recruitment of software engineers	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	Begin recruitment early; use academic, RSE, and open science networks for advertisement; involve institutional staff and existing RSE collaborators to maintain progress
Technical complexity or scope creep	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	Use agile, phased development plan with clear milestones; focus on core features and minimum viable product first; engage developers with experience in modular software design
Low user adoption or engagement	Likelihood: low Impact: high	Build on strong community support; continue consultations; prioritise user-friendliness of interfaces and comprehensive training materials
Sustainability after funding period	Likelihood: medium Impact: high	Host and maintain within NIOO-KNAW and SPI-Birds infrastructure; ensure open-source codebase supports reuse; pursue additional funding through aligned initiatives
Integration with external tools	Likelihood: low Impact: medium	Design modular export/import functionality; use open standards; engage potential partners and users early in the process

Word count SEC43 (max. 150): 148

4.4 Budget

Summary of Personnel Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institution	Total FTE	Years active	Amount

Summary of Material & IT Budget

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
work performed by third parties	consultation of two RSEs from the FAIRBiRDS project during project recruitment and technical scoping phases	2 people x 10 hr x €75/hr	€ 1,500.00
work performed by third parties	knowledge valorisation costs: preparation of a user manual	20 hr x €50/hr	€ 1,000.00
national symposium/conference/workshop organised by the project itself;	organisation of four workshops (2 x online, 2 x in-person) for potential users at the end of the project	catering for 2 x ~25 person in-person workshops	€ 800.00
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	presentation in at least two conferences (1 x national (e.g., Netherlands Annual Ecology Meetings), 1 x international (e.g., European Ornithologists' Union, Hole-nesting Birds Meeting), including registration, travel, and accommodations	1 person x attendance at NAEM (€500); 2 person x attendance at EOU (€1,500)	€ 3,500.00
knowledge dissemination costs	design and distribution costs for promotional (infographics, flyers, etc.), translational services, and targeted advertisements aimed at broadening the SPI-Birds Network of contributors	design costs: 20 hr x €50/hr (in-house); printing: ~€250	€ 1,250.00
knowledge dissemination costs	vendor / booth fees at at least two conferences (in addition to those mentioned above)	2 x €1,000 booth fee (e.g., at EOU)	€ 2,000.00
costs for Open Access publishing (solely in full gold Open Access journals, registered in the "Directory of Open Access Journals")	publication costs (e.g., Methods in Ecology & Evolution "Application" article about the DES)	1 x APC for MEE Application article + VAT (21%)	€ 2,652.32

Total Personnel requested: €237.260,50 (2.35 FTE)

Total Material/IT requested: €12.702,32

Total budget requested: €249.962,82

4.5 Budget justification

We will appoint two research software engineers on 1.1 FTE (or equivalent part-time; ~1,500 h) contracts, who will lead the project's technical development. Their profiles and compensation (estimated CAO scale 10.8; HOT 2.1–11) follow the eScience Center's RSE Level 2 role [8] and reflect market-aligned rates.

The SPI-Birds core team will largely contribute in-kind, with limited reimbursement for project coordination, community consultations and testing. To ensure the project receives the necessary guidance, the budget includes ████████ JBB's time ████████ in both years and ████████ JR's time ████████ in Year 2 for application deployment. Additional funds are allocated to knowledge valorisation activities, including virtual workshops, participation in conferences, and development of training materials. These efforts are essential to promote adoption, engage users beyond the SPI-Birds Network, and further long-term impacts.

Technical services related to hosting and deployment will be supported by ICT at NIOO-KNAW. A server for hosting the repository, database, and web-application has already been acquired. The budget reflects a lean structure prioritising recruitment of the necessary expertise for the project's success, sustainability, and community uptake. Long-term hosting and maintenance by NIOO-KNAW will ensure continued access beyond the grant period.

Word count SEC 45 (max. 200): 199

4.6 Impact plan

SPI-BirDES will improve data quality, transparency, and reusability in long-term ecological research. By enabling structured data entry using open standards, the platform will promote FAIR data practices from the point of collection [9] and, together with existing SPI-Birds infrastructure, at every step of the data life cycle (Figure 1). This will enhance reproducibility, support data preservation, and facilitate reuse across ecological contexts.

The platform will directly benefit researchers engaged in monitoring birds, especially members of the SPI-Birds Network, which currently includes some 165 studies across more than 30 countries. In our recent survey, nearly all respondents (98%) supported the proposal and 90% indicated they would consider adopting the platform. These results signal strong interest and potential for uptake and impact across a broad international community.

Concrete activities to support this impact include virtual design consultations, pilot testing with key users, conference presentations, and training materials to support users in adopting the DES. Outreach will also target adjacent research communities who collect similar data types but lack open, shared data entry tools.

Beyond research, **SPI-BirDES** will support responsible stewardship of biodiversity data, increasing transparency and trust. This will engender broader societal impacts, including evidence-based policy, conservation planning, and public science engagement.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 200

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

The primary outcomes of this project will be the Data Entry Software (DES) and associated training and documentation materials. The DES will consist of two interoperating, open-source applications (web-based and desktop), a modular codebase hosted on GitHub, and integration pathways (“middle layers”) connecting to other SPI-Birds infrastructure, including pipelines and the repository.

To ensure sustainability, three types of resources are needed:

1. **Personnel** to manage ongoing development and respond to user feedback;
2. **Technical infrastructure** for hosting the web application and maintaining the codebase and documentation;
3. **Community engagement** to ensure the software evolves in line with user needs.

SPI-BirDES will be embedded with SPI-Birds infrastructure hosted at NIOO-KNAW, where it is part of the institute’s core digital research infrastructure. Institutional ICT will support maintenance of the physical and online infrastructure, including setup of a dedicated server for the web-based platform and website maintenance. Software documentation, user guides, and GitHub repositories will be maintained by the SPI-Birds core team, who have all the necessary expertise in data management, pipeline development, and community governance, and who are (permanently) employed in roles that enable their continued long-term engagement.

To reduce reliance on a single funding source, SPI-Birds will seek additional support through other open science calls, data management and interoperability projects, and institutional partnerships. We will also engage the SPI-Birds Network to identify opportunities for larger, collaborative proposals and “crowdsourced” financial or technical support for upgrading and long-term maintenance of the DES. The platform’s modular design and open licensing will also facilitate community-driven development and integration into other local, national, and international infrastructure efforts.

By embedding **SPI-BirDES** within an active, well-supported, and growing research community, and by maintaining open, standards-based code and workflows, we aim to ensure the platform’s usability, availability, and extensibility long after the project ends.

Word count SEC51 (max 300): 296

Section 5.2. Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

SPI-BirDES is an open-source data entry platform designed for researchers studying populations of individually marked breeding birds. It will support structured, standardised, and FAIR-compliant entry of field data, including the core data currently standardised by the SPI-Birds data sharing initiative (broods, captures, individuals, locations, measurements, experiments). The intended audience includes members of the SPI-Birds Network and other ecological monitoring communities with similar data needs. **SPI-BirDES** will be available as both a web application and standalone desktop tool, tailored to varying technical environments and user preferences.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

Versioning will be managed through Git/GitHub. Semantic versioning (e.g., v1.0.0, etc.) will be used to distinguish between stable releases, ongoing development, and minor fixes. Releases will be tagged and archived with change logs to ensure transparency as the software develops over time.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

All source code will be hosted on a public GitHub repository and released under the permissive Apache 2.0 licence, enabling reuse, modification, and redistribution. Major releases will also be archived via Zenodo with persistent DOIs for traceability and attribution.

We will host downloadable installation files for the desktop application on the SPI-Birds website. The web application will be accessible through a committed web portal, connected to a dedicated server at NIOO-KNAW. Users will also have the option to host their own instance/branch of the web application on local servers.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

Each stable release will be archived with a DOI on Zenodo. The GitHub repository and desktop installation package will include a `CITATION.cff` (Citation File Format) file to enable standard software citation formats (e.g., BibTeX). Citation instructions will also be included in the documentation and on the website.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

User documentation will be created in markdown and published as HTML documents through an online documentation site (e.g., via GitHub Pages). PDFs of all documentation will be stored in the SPI-Birds Documentation repository on GitHub and will also be downloadable from the website and directly through the DES. Other documentation will include tutorials, example workflows, FAQs, and videos.

Developer documentation will be prepared alongside development and embedded in the codebase (i.e., via in-line comments) and GitHub wikis, detailing module structure, dependencies, and contribution guidelines. This information will be iteratively updated throughout development.

Installation requirements will be documented in the repository `README.md` and a setup guide. A desktop installer will be provided with clear system requirements.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

Contribution guidelines will be published in a `CONTRIBUTING.md` file in the GitHub repository. These will describe coding standards, how to submit issues or pull requests, and the code review process. Governance will follow the SPI-Birds structure, with development priorities set by the core team in consultation with the Advisory Board and Network members.

7. How will your software be tested?

Core functionality (e.g., data validation, import/export) will be covered by automated tests during development. Manual testing will occur during alpha and beta testing phases, with structured feedback from volunteer users. Bugs and feature issues will be tracked through GitHub.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

All dependencies will be reviewed for licence compatibility with Apache 2.0 or similar. We will use standard tools (e.g., code libraries and packages like `license-checker`, `pip-licenses`) during the technical scoping phase of the project and throughout development to audit dependencies and ensure compliance.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

The web application will be deployed via a server at NIOO-KNAW, and the desktop version will be available as downloadable installers (Windows, MacOS, Linux). Both will be distributed via GitHub releases and linked via the SPI-Birds website.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

Basic support will be provided by the SPI-Birds team via a dedicated email and GitHub, which will be checked at least weekly. Users will be encouraged to submit bug reports and feature requests via GitHub issues, where they can be tracked and prioritised by the technical team. For general questions and peer advice, a community-driven model will be encouraged through GitHub Discussions and FAQs. We have also planned for the organisation of workshops (see budget) near the end of the project to guide users through the initial set up and navigation of the system.

Maintenance of core tools and user engagement will be coordinated by the SPI-Birds technical team at NIOO-KNAW. Issues will be triaged by the SPI-Birds team, who will regularly monitor submissions. Support documentation will be continuously updated based on user feedback.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

The software will be hosted on infrastructure managed by NIOO-KNAW ICT personnel, where the SPI-Birds core team is based. For at least three years following the project completion, the SPI-Birds team and in-house database manager will oversee maintenance of the DES, ensuring server uptime, performing bug fixes, handling security updates, and responding to user issues. This post-project period is also anticipated to have the highest level of community development activity, with new users tailoring the system to their needs, developing customised middle layers to interface with in-house data management structures, and building new modules for managing other data types. Engaging SPI-Birds contributors in module expansion, interoperability challenges, and system refinement will be key to the platform's long-term success. Modules contributed by SPI-Birds users will be reviewed for compatibility with the existing system via the SPI-Birds code review process developed as part of another project (*CoreBirds*).

The software's modular, open design ensures that others can reuse or adapt components, reducing the risk of technical obsolescence. Community contributions and feature requests will be managed through GitHub, coordinated by the SPI-Birds team. All code and documentation will remain openly available and version controlled.

In the long-term, the platform will be maintained as part of SPI-Birds' ecosystem of research support infrastructures. Additional funding for feature expansion, interface updates, or adaptation to new communities will be sought through open science calls and strategic partnerships. Governance and development priorities will be guided by community feedback and the SPI-Birds Advisory Board.

Section 6: References

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- [7] Netherlands eScience Center (2023). What is a Research Software Engineer? A definition provided by the Netherlands eScience Center. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7994286>
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Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.